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RETHINKING THE TWO-TIER BUDGETING APPROACH: IMPERATIVES FOR REFORM

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ABSTRACT

This paper revisits the Two-Tier Budgeting Approach (2TBA) introduced in 2016 as part of public financial management reforms which separates ongoing commitments (Tier 1) from new or expanded proposals (Tier 2) to enhance predictability, transparency, and prioritization. A review of budget data and expenditure patterns, shows that the persistent expansion of Tier 1 levels created a rigid budget structure, limiting fiscal space for strategic investments and weakening fiscal consolidation. Weak performance evaluation mechanisms, limited monitoring and evaluation, and the absence of a transparent mechanisms for reviewing Tier 1 compounded this issue. Without improving evaluation, underperforming programs risk continued funding without accountability. The paper underscores the need to rigorously assess the trade-offs of incremental and historical budgeting and calls for a reformed 2TBA anchored on results-based monitoring, data-driven decision-making, and participatory budget evaluation to strengthen fiscal discipline and promote more equitable and evidence-informed national budgeting.

RETHINKING THE TWO-TIER BUDGETING APPROACH: IMPERATIVES FOR REFORM

*by Johnry A. Castillo**

I. INTRODUCTION

In 2015, the Department of Budget and Management (DBM) introduced the Two-Tier Budgeting Approach (2TBA) to reform the budget preparation process. The framework aimed to strengthen fiscal discipline and improve planning by separating budget proposals into two tiers: Tier 1 for the costs of ongoing programs and Tier 2 for new or expanded initiatives. While this approach enhanced predictability, nearly a decade of implementation has revealed a significant unintended consequence—an over-reliance on historical budgeting. This has caused the budget for ongoing commitments (Tier 1) to grow steadily, dramatically shrinking the fiscal space available for new and innovative priorities (Tier 2). If unaddressed, this trend risks creating a rigid budget that crowds out strategic investments and undermines the government's fiscal consolidation efforts.

This paper provides a critical, evidence-based assessment of the 2TBA's performance from 2016 to 2025, examining its impact on three core public financial management objectives: aggregate fiscal discipline, strategic resource allocation, and operational efficiency. By analyzing observable trends in national and sectoral budget data, this paper identifies the 2TBA's strengths and structural challenges. It concludes with policy options for enhancing 2TBA implementation, ensuring stronger alignment between planning and budgeting, and embedding the approach within ongoing PFM reform legislation¹.

It is important to note that this review does not offer a detailed agency-level performance analysis. Instead, it provides a high-level overview based on publicly available DBM documents and aggregated data. The findings should therefore be interpreted as an analysis of observable trends rather than a comprehensive evaluation of the 2TBA's overall impact.

II. THE 2TBA: ORIGINS AND MECHANICS OF THE BUDGET PREPARATION REFORM

The 2TBA emerged from a long trajectory of public financial management (PFM) reforms aimed at improving fiscal governance and linking planning with budgeting. Early reform

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¹ Pending bills include House Bill Nos. 00019, 00418, 03419, 04114, 04260, 04650, 05266, 06384, 07749, 08087, among others.

efforts began with the Public Expenditure Management Improvement Program (PEMIP) in 1998, which introduced:

- The Medium-Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF) – strategic, multi-year budgeting;
- The Organizational Performance Indicator Framework (OPIF) – linking budgets to measurable outputs; and
- Sectoral Efficiency and Effectiveness Reviews (SEERs) – evaluating spending efficiency (Capistrano, 2017).

These measures, however, remained inadequate. The 2010 Public Expenditure and Financial Accountability (PEFA) assessment² identified persistent weaknesses: fragmented budget preparation, poor linkage between goals and resource allocation, a complicated fund release process, and executive flexibility that enabled mid-year spending changes (World Bank, 2010).

Prior to 2TBA, budget preparation suffered from procedural inefficiencies. Notable among these is the undifferentiated agency submissions that mixed ongoing and new spending which lead to resource-intensive technical budget hearings (TBHs). To address this, the DBM introduced the 2TBA via National Budget Memorandum (NBM) No. 123 for the FY 2016 budget cycle, creating a more predictable and streamlined process.

The 2TBA framework operates within the budget preparation phase³, which runs from January to July each year. As illustrated in *Figure 1*, the process begins with the Budget Call, which sets submission protocols, forms, timelines, and applicable expenditure frameworks, including the 2TBA. The core reform is the separation of budget deliberations into two distinct tiers:

- **Tier 1 – Forward Estimates (FEs):** three-year projections of ongoing program costs, serving as hard ceilings for existing PAPs. These are updated annually based on macroeconomic assumptions, inflation, exchange rates, and utilization rates. Tier 1 covers, among others:
 - o Salaries and pensions for existing positions;
 - o Recurring services (e.g., PSA surveys, COMELEC elections);
 - o Multi-year contractual obligations; and
 - o Ongoing infrastructure and non-infrastructure projects.

² A standardized framework used to assess the performance of a country's public financial management (PFM) system. It was developed by a partnership of international organizations including the World Bank, IMF, European Commission, and others.

³ The national budget process comprises four phases: **preparation, legislation, execution, and accountability**. Budget preparation runs from January until the President approves the National Expenditure Program (NEP) in July

FIGURE I
BUDGET PREPARATION PHASE AND THE 2TBA

Source: DBM

- **Tier 2 – New or expanded initiatives** guided by the **Budget Priorities Framework (BPF)**, which identifies strategic sectors and programs eligible for funding based on fiscal space. Examples include:

- o New infrastructure or ICT projects;
- o Organizational restructuring or program expansion;
- o New positions and performance-based incentives; and
- o Maintenance of newly completed facilities or equipment.⁴

Following the Budget Call, agencies submit their consolidated Tier 1 and Tier 2 proposals online.⁵ Submissions must align with the Philippine Development Plan (PDP), and the BPF, and demonstrate implementation readiness (*e.g.*, feasibility studies, procurement plans, regulatory permits). Thereafter, DBM reviews the proposals through **TBHs** and internal advisories, followed by **two rounds of executive review**—Preliminary and Final—before recommending levels to agencies.⁶ Final recommendations go to the Cabinet for scrutiny and to the President for approval. The approved Tier 1 and selected Tier 2 items form the NEP, which is submitted to Congress.

III. 2TBA BUDGET COMPOSITION

An examination of the 2TBA from FY 2016 to 2025 shows a consistent budget pattern: Tier 1 comprised an average of 50.9% of the total ceiling, Automatic Appropriations and Special Purpose Funds (SPFs) accounted for 37.8%, and Tier 2 comprised only 11.4% (*Figure 2*).

This distribution underscores the growing rigidity of the budget structure. Nearly 90% of the budget is pre-allocated for existing programs or mandatory obligations—leaving very limited room for new or emerging priorities (*Figure 2, Table 1*). The declining fiscal space for Tier 2 is

⁴ *Annex A, National Budget Memorandum No. 153, December 2024.*

⁵ *Agencies submit consolidated proposals via the Online Submission of Budget Proposal System (OSBPS), incorporating Tier 1 adjustments and Tier 2 requests (General Submission Requirements, NBM No. 153).*

⁶ *Annex C, NBM No. 153*

especially concerning during economic shocks or in addressing urgent national issues such as health emergencies, infrastructure recovery, or climate resilience.

Table 1 reveals instances where the NEP exceeded the DBCC-approved ceiling (notably in 2019 and 2021) and years where fiscal space for Tier 2 turned negative (2024 and 2025) due to expanding Tier 1 commitments. In 2025, for example, Tier 1 requirements reached P3.38 trillion, while available space for Tier 2 fell to a negative P193.1 billion.⁷ These were offset only by adjustments to the final NEP to accommodate government priorities. These figures highlight how expanding baseline commitments can crowd out discretionary spending. Such trends underscore the need to periodically reassess Tier 1 commitments through performance-based reviews or strategic expenditure reviews. Without this, the budget risks becoming a rigid financial plan with limited adaptability, potentially undermining fiscal prudence.

TABLE I
2TBA BUDGET COMPOSITION, 2016-2025
AMOUNT IN BILLION PESOS

Year	Tier 1					Tier 2		Total		
	Ongoing PAPs	%	Auto	%	Total	Tier 2/ Fiscal Spare	%	Budget Ceiling	NEP	Variance
2016	1,462.7	48.8	956.4	31.9	2,419.1	580.9	19.4	3,000.0	3,002.0	2.0
2017	1,697.1	50.7	1,065.4	31.8	2,762.5	587.5	17.5	3,350.0	3,350.0	-
2018	1,950.6	50.8	1,236.5	32.2	3,187.1	652.9	17.0	3,840.0	3,767.0	(73.0)
2019	1,847.8	53.3	1,258.4	36.3	3,106.2	362.3	10.4	3,468.5	3,757.0	288.5
2020	1,842.7	44.9	1,345.7	32.8	3,188.4	911.6	22.2	4,100.0	4,100.0	-
2021	1,767.3	40.8	1,726.2	39.8	3,493.5	841.7	19.5	4,335.2	4,506.0	170.8
2022	2,742.5	54.6	1,951.3	38.8	4,693.8	329.8	6.6	5,023.6	5,024.0	0.4
2023	2,792.5	53.0	2,228.1	42.3	5,020.6	247.4	4.7	5,268.0	5,268.0	-
2024	3,288.5	57.2	2,477.7	43.1	5,766.2	(15.6)	(0.3)	5,750.6	5,768.0	17.4
2025	3,380.4	54.5	3,012.7	48.6	6,393.1	(193.1)	(3.1)	6,200.0	6,352.0	152.0
Avg.	2,277.2	50.9	1,725.8	37.8	4,003.1	430.5	11.4	-	-	558.1

**For 2016 to 2022, this includes (e.g., NTA, net lending, among others) and special purpose funds (SPF) as applicable (e.g., National Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Fund, special shares to LGUs, contingent fund, debt interest payments, among others), based on NBM for BPF (2016-2022). For 2023-2025, the amount includes lumpsum SPF and Automatic Appropriation.
Note: Figures may not add up due to rounding off; Source: DBM*

Table 2 presents selected agency 2TBA composition for 2019 and 2021. Tier 1 of the Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH) which was only P123.9 billion for 2019 was ramped up to P555.7 billion in the 2019 NEP. This was an increase of about P431.8 billion

⁷ National Budget Memorandum No. 152, April 30, 2024, "Budget Priorities Framework for the Preparation of the FY

which consumed the available fiscal space of P362.3 billion. Notably, the Tier 1 levels of DSWD, DOH and DA were reduced by P9.4 billion, P5.6 billion and P1.6 billion, respectively, to accommodate such increase for the DPWH. The DA and DSWD adjustments were made due to dismal performance and by recomputing the cash-based requirements of their PAPs.⁸

In 2021, the Tier 1 ceiling of DPWH amounting to P150.7 billion was adjusted to P666.5 billion in the FY 2021 NEP. This represents an increase of about P515.8 billion covering 61.3% of the fiscal space. During this period, several agencies also received substantial additional allocation under Tier 2: Department of Education (DepEd) with an increase of P93.2 billion (11.1%), Department of Health (DOH) with P57.7 billion (6.9%), Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) with P41.1 billion (4.9%), and Budgetary Support to Government Corporations (BSGC) with P25.6 billion (3.0%), respectively.

TABLE 2
SELECTED AGENCY 2TBA COMPOSITION,
(AMOUNTS IN BILLION PESOS), 2019 AND 2021

Agency	2019				2021			
	Tier 1	Tier 2	NEP	% Share to Fiscal Space	Tier 1	Tier 2	NEP	% Share to Fiscal Space
Department of Agriculture (DA)	49.0	(1.6)	47.4	(0.4)	42.8	21.1	64.0	2.5
Department of Education (DepEd)	494.3	4.0	498.3	1.1	475.4	93.2	568.7	11.1
State Universities and Colleges (SUCs)	59.6	2.0	61.6	0.5	54.8	24.4	79.2	2.9
Department of Health (DOH)	76.6	(5.6)	71.0	(1.5)	70.0	57.7	127.8	6.9
Department of Public Works and Highways (DPWH)	123.9	431.8	555.7	119.2	150.7	515.8	666.5	61.3
Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD)	146.0	(9.4)	136.7	(2.6)	129.9	41.1	171.0	4.9
Budgetary Support to Government Corporations (BSGC)	105.4	81.3	186.7	22.4	121.7	25.6	147.4	3.0
Total	1,847.8	362.3	3,757.0	138.7	1,767.3	841.7	4,506.0	92.5

Source of basic data: NBM 130 and 136, NEP 2019-2021

⁸ Rey, Aika (2019). *Winners and losers under Duterte's 2019 budget*. <https://www.rappler.com/newsbreak/in-depth/229539-winners-losers-national-budget-philippines-2019/>

IV. IMPROVEMENTS IN THE BUDGET PREPARATION PROCESS

The implementation of the 2TBA helped address limitations in traditional annual budgeting by introducing key procedural and structural improvements. The notable improvements include:

- 1) Strengthening institutional processes to support more efficient and strategic budget preparation.** The DBM (2017) points out that by segregating PAPs by Tiers 1 and 2, the 2TBA enhanced and simplified budget preparation procedures.⁹ For example, under Tier 1, budgetary requirements for Personnel Services (PS) can easily be determined and set aside from deliberations which unduly prolong the TBH in the past. Note that PS requirement for regular agencies, Constitutionally Fiscal Autonomous Group (CFAG) and other agencies with special requirements have specific considerations.

Under Tier 1, CFAG agencies received 100% requirement for salaries and allowances for both filled and unfilled positions recorded in the Government Manpower Information System (GMIS), including pension and retirement gratuity for existing retirees. Meanwhile, regular agencies' salaries for filled positions are provided under regular agency budgets, while 30% of the cost for unfilled civilian positions is charged to the Miscellaneous Personnel Benefits Fund (MPBF). There are specific agencies receiving 100% funding for new positions in Tier 1 (e.g., teachers, military, and medical personnel), and pension payments for specific groups like CHR retirees.¹⁰

Under Tier 2, funding covers: 1) pension for new retirees after the cut-off date, 2) adjustments due to new programs, structural changes, or transfer of functions, 3) additional contractual/casual positions for ongoing projects, 4) approved staffing modifications and new positions (up to 100%), and up to 75% for new civilian positions with proper documentation, and 5) step increments and overtime pay per relevant joint circulars. There were PS items placed under the MPBF and pension and gratuity fund (PGF), that could be ascertained with the aid of 2TBA presented in the annual budget call.

Moreover, distinctions on which Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) and Capital Outlays (CO) should be under Tier 1 or Tier 2 were also highlighted. For example, Tier 1 MOOE includes budget requirements for: 1) regular periodic activities or programs (PSA Survey, COMELEC election); 2) those regular and recurring services covered by contracts or Multi-Year Contractual Authority (MYCA); and 3) those with

⁹ *Guide to the Two Tier Budget Approach (2TBA): A Tool for Agencies, DBM, 2017*

¹⁰ *Annex A, NBM No. 153, National Budget Call for FY 2026*

approved Foreign-Assisted Projects covered by Forward Obligational Authorities and Loan Agreement, etc.

On the other hand, Tier 2 MOOE covers: 1) costs to implement approved major changes in the organization or structure of an agency, including downsizing or mergers; 2) those not included in the forward estimates (FEs) due to changes in demand-driven parameters of Medium-Term Expenditure Plans (MTEP) and already approved rolling development or expansion plans; 3) new/expanded ICT PAPs; and 4) maintenance costs and spare parts for projects to be completed in the current year. **Annex** provides detailed breakdown of the distinctions between these expense classes, aiding implementing agencies in segregating their funding requirements.¹¹

- 2) **Simplified budget calendar.** As identified in the budget calls from 2017 to 2019, the calendar of activities included a separate set of activity for: 1) technical budget hearings (TBHs) for Tier 1; 2) DBM review of proposals for Tier 1; and 3) presentation of the recommended levels to the Cabinet and the President for approval. However, starting with the issuance of NBM No. 133¹² for the 2021 budget call, the process was further simplified by reducing the number of steps from 23 to 16, resulting in a simplified workflow.

FIGURE 3
CALENDAR OF ACTIVITIES, 2017-2025

2017	2019	2021	2023	2025
1 Issuance of Budget Call	1 Issuance of Budget Call	1 Issuance of Budget Call	1 Issuance of Budget Call	1 Issuance of Budget Call
2-3 Budget Forum	2-3 Budget Forum	2 Budget Forum	2-3 Budget Forum	2-3 Budget Forum
4-5 Consultations	4-5 Consultations	3-4 Consultations	4-5 Consultations	4-5 Consultations
6 Submission of PY Actual Obligations	6 Submission of PY Actual Obligations	5 Submission of PY Actual Obligations	6 Submission of PY Actual Obligations	6 Submission of PY Actual Obligations
7 Deadline of Submission for T1 (FEs)	7 Consultation with Agencies for Formulated T1	6 Issuance of NBM for BPF	7 Issuance of BPF	7 Issuance of BPF
8 TBH with Agencies for T1	8 Presentation to DBM Secretary of Tier 1 Level	7 Submission of Tier 1 and 2 budget proposals	8-10 Submission of budget proposals and conduct of TBH Presentation to DBM Secretary of Tier 1 Level	8-10 Submission of budget proposals and conduct of TBH Presentation to DBM Secretary of Tier 1 Level
9 DBM Review T1	9 Sending of CLs	8-9 Conduct of TBH/ ERB	11 Sending of CLs	11 Sending of CLs
10 Sending of CLs	10 Presentation to the Cabinet and President and Approval of Tier 1	10 Sending of CLs	12-14 Presentation to the Cabinet and President of the proposed budget levels for Approval	12-14 Presentation to the Cabinet and President of the proposed budget levels for Approval
11 Presentation to the Cabinet and President and Approval of Tier 1	11 Issuance of Hard Ceiling and BPF	11-14 Presentation to the Cabinet and President of the proposed budget levels for Approval	15 Submission of NEP to Congress	15 Submission of NEP to Congress
12 Issuance of Hard Ceiling	12-14 Review of Tier 2	15 Submission of NEP to Congress	16 Submission of NEP to Congress	16 Submission of NEP to Congress
13-17 Review of Tier 2	15 Sending of CL for Total Level			
18 Sending of CL for Total Level	16-19 President's Approval and finalization			
19-22 President's Approval and finalization	20 Submission of NEP to Congress			
23 Submission of NEP to Congress				

Source: DBM National Budget Memoranda No. 149, 145, 142, 138, 133, 131, 129, 127, 125

¹¹ NBM No. 153, National Budget Call for FY 2026

¹² NBM No. 133, National Budget Call for FY 2021

- 3) **Greater Transparency through publication of Tier 1 ceilings.** The DBM began publishing Tier 1 ceilings which represent FEs for ongoing programs over a three-year horizon. These ceilings are released as annexes to the annual Budget Call/Budget Priorities Framework (BPF) and serve as hard budget limits that agencies must work within. Tier 1 items include funding requirements that can be identified with certainty such as regular and recurring services covered by contracts or Multi-Year Contractual Authority (MYCA), and approved locally funded projects covered by MYCA.

TABLE 3
PUBLISHED TIER I (FORWARD ESTIMATES)
(AMOUNTS IN BILLION PESOS), 2020-2026

Year	Programmed	Updated	Variance	% change	Growth Rate
2020	1,842.7	1,842.7	-	-	(0.3)
2021	1,840.3	1,767.3	(73.0)	(4.0)	(4.1)
2022	1,522.6	2,742.5	1,219.9	80.1	55.2
2023	2,792.5	2,792.5	-	-	1.8
2024	3,288.5	3,288.5	-	-	17.8
2025	3,196.9	3,380.4	183.5	5.7	2.8
2026	3,154.0	3,863.8	709.8	22.5	14.3

Note: In the absence of published FEs for FY 2022, outyear levels (2023-2024) accounted for the levels issued annually in the NBM for the purpose (NBM No. 142 and 147)
Source: DBM NBM (2020-2026)

Table 3 presents published Tier 1 and its comparison with the updated Tier 1 levels from 2020 to 2026. As can be recalled from earlier discussion, the estimated Tier 1 levels are updated in the next budget year to account for changes in inflation, foreign exchange, and absorptive capacities. FY 2022 show an alarming increase of P1.2 trillion or 80.1% increase from the programmed level due to modification of items for COVID-19 recovery efforts¹³. In 2026, there was an increase of P709.8 billion or 22.5%. The inconsistent publication of Forward Estimates (FEs), particularly in 2022, hinders meaningful comparison of programmed outyear levels (e.g., 2023–2024). Nevertheless, the disclosure of Tier 1 levels marks a step toward greater transparency, enabling the public to assess budget predictability and hold the government accountable for annual and medium-term budget formulation.

¹³ NBM No. 141, June 2021

- 4) **Stronger alignment with national planning processes.** New and ongoing infrastructure projects require the prior evaluation of Department of Economy, Planning, and Development (DEPDev) through the Board Committee on Infrastructure for inclusion in the Three-Year Rolling Infrastructure Program (TRIP) and Public Investment Program (PIP).¹⁴ Infrastructure projects with cost of at least P2.5 billion need to pass through the NEDA Investment Coordination Committee (ICC). R&D proposals require endorsement of supervising agencies for specific sectors (agriculture, science and technology) and Program Convergence Budgets (PCB) need the approval of PCB lead agencies. This institutional process ensures that proposals are properly vetted for alignment with sectoral and national priorities. Without the required endorsements, proposals are considered incomplete and are therefore at higher risk of being deprioritized or rejected—especially given the constraints of a limited fiscal space.¹⁵

- 5) **Avenue for CSO Participation.** FY 2016 also marked the institutionalization of civil society organization (CSO) participation in the budget preparation phase as a response to clamor of the CSO groups and other stakeholders to have more budget transparency and accountability in agency financial operations.¹⁶ As part of their budget proposals, agencies were required to submit a budget form detailing their consultation with CSO partners as co-implementers or beneficiaries. It was also intended to strengthen the conduct of agency consultations at the central and regional levels securing feedback and inputs on the proposed PAPs of agencies.

V. IMPLICATIONS ON PFM OBJECTIVES

This section focuses on the indicative outcomes and results of these changes, measured against the standard PFM criteria.

On Fiscal Discipline

Evidence from international studies confirms that budget preparation reforms—especially those enhancing the authority of the budget ministry, setting hard ceilings, and consolidating fiscal decisions—can strengthen fiscal discipline (Alesina & Perotti, 1996; International Monetary Fund, 2019; Barbier-Gauchard, et. Al, 2021; Hemming, 2023). In theory, the 2TBA aligns with these best practices by creating predictable baselines (Tier 1) and a controlled process for allocating limited fiscal space (Tier 2).

¹⁴ *Specific Submission Requirements, NBM No. 153*

¹⁵ *NBM Nos. 151 and 153*

¹⁶ *NBM No. 123, January 2015*

One measure of fiscal discipline looks at fiscal deficit over time, especially when viewed in the context of medium-term fiscal sustainability (IMF, 2013). Year-on-year (YoY) changes in fiscal deficits offer an important lens through which to assess the effectiveness of budget preparation reforms. Thus, a declining or stable deficit following the implementation of a reform suggests improved fiscal discipline—manifested through more credible budgeting, better expenditure control, and a stronger alignment between policy objectives and available resources (World Bank, 2013). *Table 4* details the trend (both in nominal and as % of GDP) and YOY percentage (%) change in government fiscal operations deficit from 2010 to 2025.

TABLE 4
YEAR-ON-YEAR (YOY) CHANGE IN GOVERNMENT FISCAL OPERATIONS DEFICIT TRENDS
(AMOUNTS IN BILLION PESOS), 2010-2025

Year	Overall Surplus / (Deficit)	% of GDP	Year on Year (YOY) %
2010	(314.5)	(3.35)	5.3
2011	(197.8)	(1.95)	(37.1)
2012	(242.8)	(2.20)	22.8
2013	(164.1)	(1.36)	(32.4)
2014	(73.1)	(0.55)	(55.4)
2015	(121.7)	(0.87)	66.5
2016	(353.4)	(2.34)	190.4
2017	(350.6)	(2.12)	(0.8)
2018	(558.3)	(3.1)	59.2
2019	(660.2)	(3.4)	18.3
2020	(1,371.4)	(7.6)	107.7
2021	(1,670.1)	(8.6)	21.8
2022	(1,614.1)	(7.3)	(3.4)
2023	(1,512.1)	(6.2)	(6.3)
2024	(1,506.4)	(5.7)	(0.4)
2025	(1,537.7)	(5.3)	3.6

Source: DBM Fiscal Statistics Handbook

Fiscal deficit trends (*Table 4*) show mixed results during the 2TBA period. Deficits surged sharply in 2016 and 2020 by 190.4% and 107.7%, respectively, due to expansionary fiscal policy and pandemic-related spending, but moderated between 2022 and 2024, with a decline from 7.3% to 5.7% of GDP. This suggests partial progress toward fiscal consolidation, even amid elevated spending. Although the years 2022-2024 recorded a decreasing YOY change in the fiscal deficit, higher-than-programmed expenditures continued to drive elevated deficit levels, particularly in 2023 and 2024.

FIGURE 4
TIER I LEVELS AND GROWTH RATE
(AMOUNTS IN BILLION PESOS), 2016 TO 2025

Source of basic data: DBM

However, the steady growth of Tier 1 appropriations—from P1.5 trillion in 2016 to P3.4 trillion in 2025—has significantly tightened fiscal space—equivalent to a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 9.8% (Figure 4). Automatic appropriations and SPFs have also grown rapidly, increasing baseline rigidity and reducing flexibility for new priorities. Without periodic reassessment of ongoing commitments, fiscal space for Tier 2 could remain under persistent pressure.

FIGURE 5
2TBA BREAKDOWN
(AMOUNTS IN BILLION PESOS), 2016 TO 2025

Source: DBM Fiscal Statistics Handbook

As shown in *Figure 5*, with an increasing Tier 1, automatic appropriations and special purpose funds (SPFs), there is increasing rigidity in expenditure due to consistently high growth in baseline and automatic spending which highlights the need to assess the long-term sustainability of the current fiscal path.

The PEFA framework’s **Expenditure Composition Outturn** indicator supports this mixed picture. Pre-2TBA (2012–2014), the Philippines scored poorly (D overall; C by economic classification).¹⁷ Under 2TBA (2021–2023), variance improved to under 10%, earning a score of B—suggesting better alignment between approved budgets and actual spending. Yet sustaining this requires consistent enforcement of spending limits within categories and minimizing mid-year reallocations (*Table 5*).

TABLE 5
EXPENDITURE COMPOSITION OUTTURN BASED ON ECONOMIC CLASSIFICATION
(AMOUNTS IN BILLION PESOS), 2012-2014 vs 2021-2023

Year	Appropriation*	Expenditure	Deviation	Variance	Score
2012	2,121.8	1,790.9	253.0	14.1%	C
2013	2,355.3	1,985.0	292.8	14.8%	C
2014	2,586.3	1,964.7	498.9	25.4%	D
2021	4,737.2	4,675.7	415.8	8.9%	B
2022	4,954.6	5,159.6	161.7	3.1%	A
2023	5,288.4	5,336.1	336.5	6.3%	B

*Select items considered under PEFA dimensions
Source of basic data: PEFA Assessment Report (2016 and 2025), DBM Annual reports 2021, 2022, 2023

In short, while the 2TBA has introduced mechanisms that can enhance fiscal discipline, its long-term impact will depend on curbing baseline expansion, integrating performance reviews into Tier 1 funding decisions, and keeping the system resistant to politically driven reallocations.

On Allocative Efficiency

The PEFA framework defines allocative efficiency as the capacity of the PFM system to align resources with strategic priorities and ensure those allocations are implemented as intended. The 2TBA supports this by establishing **Tier 1 hard ceilings** for ongoing programs and directing **Tier 2 funding** toward priority sectors through the **Budget Priorities Framework (BPF)**.

¹⁷ High score of A means variance in expenditure composition is less than 5% for at least two of the last 3 years; score of B if the variance is between 5% to 10%; C for variance between 10% to 15%; and D if the variance is more than 15%.

Once Tier 1 hard ceilings were established based on updated macroeconomic assumptions and historical performance, the DBM issues the BPF through a separate NBM which guides agencies in formulating their full budget submissions. At this point, agencies are permitted to revise expenditure details within Tier 1 ceilings based on agency priorities up to the sub-object level. Thereafter, they submit additional Tier 2 proposals, if necessary, subject to confirmation of their Tier 1 levels.

The BPF outlines strict prioritization criteria to ensure that new funding requests are aligned with national development objectives, fiscal sustainability, and sectoral priorities such as infrastructure, education, health, social protection, agriculture, and housing.¹⁸ While most agencies complied with their Tier 1 ceilings and refrained from requesting additional funds, others sought increases under Tier 2. Notably, from FY 2022 and earlier, the BPF explicitly discussed available fiscal space to promote transparency. However, beginning FY 2023, references to available fiscal space have been absent, raising concerns on the visibility of budget constraints in the prioritization process.

FIGURE 6
TRENDS IN GOVERNMENT SPENDING ON PRIORITY AND LESS-PRIORITY SETORS, 2014–2025

Source: BESF 2016-2025

Figure 6 illustrates the significant shift in funding allocation from 2014 to 2025. In the implementation of 2TBA, priority sectors were clearly defined, such as infrastructure, education, social protection, health, and agriculture, which eventually experienced steady and exponential growth in funding. In contrast, less-priority sectors, like environmental protection,

¹⁸ NBM No. 151, 2024

public order and safety, and defense, also saw an increase in funding, but at a considerably lower rate.

From 2016-2025, infrastructure spending received the biggest share, followed by education and social protection (Figure 7). This funding prioritization indicated the long-term strategy of the government to boost its development by spending for infrastructure with at least 5% of its GDP (World Bank, 2005). In 2019, the DBM reported the level of infrastructure spending at 5.5% from 2019 to 2022, nearly double the 2.8% (average) of GDP realized from 2010 to 2016. In 2023, infrastructure spending accounted for 5.8% of GDP, maintaining the same level in 2022 and exceeding the 2023 target of 5.3%. The infrastructure investment contributed 0.5 percentage point to the 5.5% increase in real GDP which helped the country remain among the top-performing economies in Asia.¹⁹

FIGURE 7
TRENDS IN GOVERNMENT SPENDING ON PRIORITY AND PRIORITY SETORS,
2014-2025

Source: BESF 2016-2025

Consequently, the obligation rate (the percentage of allocated funds committed) increased from 86.7% in 2016 to 95.2% in 2017. Obligation rate during pre-2TBA stood at 80.5% while during 2TBA (2016 onwards) obligation rates increased to an average of 94.1%. In terms of utilization (the percentage of actual disbursements relative to obligations), overall rates went up to an average of 97.4%. Particularly in 2020-2023, rates remained above 97%, peaking at 101.6% in 2021, primarily due to expeditious disbursements from several National Government Agencies (NGAs), due to COVID and timely payments for educational grants and subsidies.

¹⁹ NBM No. 152, 2024

FIGURE 8
OVERALL BUDGET DISBURSEMENT RATES, 2014-2023

Source: DBM's Annual fiscal Report, SAAOUDB, BTR Cash Operations Report

Figure 9 illustrates the changes in disbursement growth rates from 2010 to 2025. Before the 2TBA was implemented, volatility in terms of changes in disbursement growth rates were evident from 2010 to 2015. From 2016 to 2022, the average disbursement growth went up by an average rate of 12.8% while a sudden drop in disbursement growth was observed in 2023 with 3.4%. Note however that there are increases to 7.8% and 7.4% in 2024 and 2025, respectively. Nonetheless, trend from 2016 to 2025 (in orange), which coincides with the period of implementation of 2TBA, shows more controlled disbursement growth (decreasing) despite increasing trend in disbursements. However, it is noteworthy to consider that other factors could also be influencing this trend.

FIGURE 9
DISBURSEMENT GROWTH RATES, 2010-2025

Source: DBM Fiscal Statistics Handbook

These trends indicate that the 2TBA has helped channel resources toward priority sectors and improve utilization. However, the absence of published fiscal space data since FY 2023, combined with persistent funding increases for lower-priority sectors, raises concerns about transparency in trade-offs and the system’s capacity to adapt allocations to evolving priorities.

On Agency Operational Efficiency

Operational efficiency refers to the extent to which agencies convert budgetary resources into outputs and outcomes at the lowest possible cost while meeting performance targets. The 2TBA reinforces this principle by linking Tier 1 funding to **Forward Estimates (FEs)** based on historical performance, and by requiring Tier 2 proposals to demonstrate clear deliverables, cost-effectiveness, and implementation readiness.

Table 6 presents the disbursement rates from 2016 to 2023 of key agencies driving the priority sectors under the 2TBA, specifically infrastructure, education, social welfare, and health. During this period, the DepEd improved its disbursement rates, averaging 86.1%, significantly higher than the national average of 70.5%. In contrast, the DPWH, the government’s main infrastructure arm, lagged behind with an average utilization rate of only 47.4%.

**TABLE 6
DISBURSEMENTS TO TOTAL AVAILABLE APPROPRIATIONS
(UTILIZATION RATES, %), 2016-2023**

Particulars	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Avg.
Department of Agriculture	66.0	62.5	62.4	64.4	57.1	70.3	71.2	72.9	65.8
Department of Education	78.4	76.7	85.6	88.2	87.7	90.2	91.9	89.8	86.1
State Universities and Colleges	79.1	77.5	85.0	78.6	80.9	75.3	71.7	72.3	77.5
Department of Health	81.0	59.1	59.6	63.2	69.2	71.4	68.7	72.6	68.1
Department of Public Works and Highways	54.7	32.8	39.3	48.1	28.6	53.8	61.2	60.5	47.4
Department of Social Welfare and Development	72.7	80.3	81.8	77.7	83.4	82.3	80.9	81.4	80.1
Total NG	70.3	60.3	67.0	70.0	70.9	75.2	76.6	74.0	70.5

Source of basic data: SAAODB, DBM website

Similarly, the Department of Agriculture (DA) and the Department of Health (DOH) posted averages of 65.8% and 68.1%, respectively. Persistent inefficiencies in budget utilization, procurement issues, and implementation readiness—particularly agencies handling large infrastructure projects—remain a critical challenge. Despite being prioritized for increased funding under the 2TBA, these agencies continue to exhibit low absorptive capacities, raising concerns about the effectiveness of annually scaling up their budgets.

Looking at the major programs of priority agencies from 2023-2025, *Table 7* shows that most of their major programs exhibited positive growth rates except for DPWH's Network Development Program, DepEd's Basic Education Inputs Program, DSWD's Protective Social Welfare Program, DOH's Social Health Protection and DA's Technical and Support Services. Primary reason for the noted decrease is due to poor utilization of funds on infrastructure (DPWH, DepEd, and DA), low disbursement rate for medical assistance (DOH), and policy discretion reducing the 4Ps program (DSWD).

TABLE 7
BUDGET FOR MAJOR PROGRAMS AND GROWTH RATES,
2023-2025

Program	Program Budget (In Billion Pesos)			Growth Rates		Implementing Department/ Agency
	2023	2024	2025	2023-24	2024-25	
Support to Schools and Learners	560.9	570.4	600.3	1.7	5.2	DEPED
Convergence and Special Support	388.3	411.0	486.2	5.8	18.3	DPWH
Flood Management	185.8	244.6	249.8	31.7	2.1	DPWH
Asset Preservation	124.6	139.0	154.1	11.6	10.8	DPWH
Protective Social Welfare	71.1	119.3	131.8	67.7	10.5	DSWD
Network Development	119.2	132.3	112.7	11.0	(14.9)	DPWH
Health Facilities Operation	68.6	71.5	100.8	4.2	41.0	DOH
Basic Education Inputs	66.5	92.2	87.5	38.6	(5.1)	DEPED
Promotive Social Welfare	116.4	116.2	73.6	(0.2)	(36.6)	DWSD
Bridge Program	31.2	24.8	42.6	(20.7)	71.9	DPWH
Social Health Protection	33.1	59.3	42.4	79.1	(28.5)	DOH
Locally-Funded and Foreign-Assisted	14.2	20.0	35.0	40.6	75.0	DA
Technical and Support Services	35.3	37.8	32.8	7.1	(13.0)	DA
Agricultural Machinery, Equipment, Facilities and Infrastructures	25.9	29.7	30.3	14.9	2.0	DA

Source of basic data: GAA 2023-2025 and BESF 2024-2025

Disbursement patterns reveal that while obligation rates are high under 2TBA, bottlenecks persist in converting obligations into timely outputs. The 2022 and 2023 performance reports highlight recurring challenges: late procurement start dates, insufficient pre-implementation planning, and overestimation of absorptive capacity.

Overall, the 2TBA has provided a structural incentive for agencies to plan and implement more efficiently, but the absence of a **systematic, independent performance audit of Tier 1 commitments** remains a key limitation. Without this, there is a risk that underperforming programs will continue to receive baseline funding without accountability-driven adjustments.

VI. ISSUES AND CHALLENGES IN IMPLEMENTATION

While there are valid claims that the 2TBA has helped improve the overall budget preparation process, continuous implementation has presented certain risks and challenges that warrant reconsideration. Among these are:

On Procedural Matters

- 1) **Absence of comprehensive operating guidelines for evaluation.** There is a need for verifiable procedural guidelines for 2TBA to be more effective. Noticeably, evaluation procedures for computation/formulation of Tier 1 and Tier 2 are not publicly established for transparency and accountability purposes. The Local Government Code of 1991 requires the promulgation of a Budget Operations Manual for LGUs. However, budget operations manuals for NGAs and GOCCs remain absent. This absence limits the ability of agencies, CSOs, the public, and congressional oversight bodies to fully understand and assess the basis for budget decisions. This lack of transparency may contribute to perceived discretion in the evaluation process and may weaken mechanisms for effective oversight and accountability.

For example, there are ambiguity in how the policy on indexation is applied to MOOE, as well as in the benchmarking of updated Tier 1 levels—specifically between the NEP and the GAA. Also, the application of Budget Utilization Rates (BUR) requires consistency. It is important to clarify whether budget decisions are based on BUR at the level of individual PAPs, entire agencies, or whichever metric is most favorable to the agency. Without such clarity, the credibility and comparability of BUR as a decision-making tool may be undermined.

The lack of concrete and publicly accessible procedural manuals increases the risk of varied interpretations and inconsistent application during the evaluation and formulation of the national budget. Given that an average of 50.9% of the national budget is formulated or updated by the DBM under Tier 1, it is important that its recommendations—prior to Presidential approval, if at all secured—are grounded in a more transparent and evidence-based decision-making process. Strengthening this foundation would enhance both the credibility and accountability of budget allocations.

- 2) **The non-observance of regular agency TBH and subsequent President's approval for Tier 1/ FE levels.** When the 2TBA was introduced, NBM No. 123 (Budget Call for FY 2016) envisions a policy of active agency participation in formulating FEs. This design aimed to ensure that the President and Cabinet would lead in setting the strategic direction and in determining the allocation of the remaining fiscal space, facilitating a more deliberate assessment of trade-offs and opportunities.

However, while the calendar of activities based on published Budget Calls from 2016-2019 requires that Tier 1 process should undergo Cabinet and Presidential approval, it is noted that this practice was no longer observed and identified in the subsequent budget calls²⁰.

As shown in *Figure 3*, particularly during and after the pandemic—this consultative process has weakened. Not all agencies are consulted, and TBHs for Tier 1 have been discontinued. This lack of consultation risks undermining the strategic and collaborative intent of the 2TBA and could reduce the effectiveness of Tier 1 resource allocations. While this may be understandable to speed up the approval process given the limited time to prepare the NEP, the value of the iterative process particularly in the national budget and holistic participation of stakeholders cannot be undermined.

- 3) **Unclear policy guidance, coupled with the increasing number of multiyear projects supported by MYCAs.** Since items with MYCA are funded in Tier 1 for the outyear requirements, the national government is forced to fund PAPs with MYCA without clear guidance on the effect of the status of previous years' implementation. As reflected in the BESF (2025), the issued MYCAs released from 2023 to 2025 have been increasing from 130 to 252. Notably, in 2023, there was a P34.5 billion variance between the programmed amount and the actual funds provided for MYCA. There remains a lack of clear policy in two key areas: 1) when and how MYCA amounts should be revised or adjusted, including limits on the frequency of issuance/modifications; and 2) the basis for figures to be used in subsequent budget years—whether to follow the initially approved MYCA or to allow adjustments based on project performance and other relevant factors.
- 4) **CSO consultations in the budget process have often become perfunctory, serving mainly to satisfy formal compliance requirements rather than to influence policy decisions.** In many cases, agencies' submissions of CSO consultation forms are not critically reviewed or reflected in budget priorities. COA's Citizens' Participatory Audit Report notes that while CSO participation mechanisms exist through the Budget Partnership Agreements (BPAs), their recommendations are seldom discussed in depth during key evaluation stages—such as the Technical Budget Hearings (TBHs), Final Executive Review Board (FERB) deliberations. This gap underscores the need to strengthen feedback mechanisms and institutional incentives for incorporating CSO inputs into actual budget decisions, consistent with the Open Government Partnership (OGP) principles of transparency, participation, and accountability.²¹

²⁰ Various NBMs (Nos. 131, 133, 138, 142, 145, 149)

²¹ Open Government Partnership. (2023). *Independent Reporting Mechanism. Philippines results report 2019–2022*. https://www.opengovpartnership.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/Philippines_Results-Report_2019-2022.pdf

On Fiscal Discipline, Allocative and Operational Efficiency

- 1) Incremental budget increases may lead to the continued funding of unnecessary or underperforming PAPs, simply by virtue of their ongoing status rather than based on evidence of effectiveness or strategic value.** Previously, the DBM implemented ZBB evaluation wherein the performances of existing programs are evaluated and revamped, or even canceled, those which fail to meet their objectives and those which are fraught with leakages (DBM, 2017). But under the 2TBA, Tier 1 formulation/updating for ongoing PAPs are funded without such criteria. Implementing agencies will continue to receive funding for those PAPs subject only to budget utilization effects or whether they are added during the budget legislation phase.

Note however that new PAPs under Tier 2 will now be treated under Tier 1 in the subsequent budget year. Therefore, as Tier 1 increases, the amount available for Tier 2 decreases. This could be a trade-off for new and innovative PAPs that cannot be accommodated given the limited fiscal space.

- 2) Weak capacity of implementing agencies to develop evidence-based Tier 2 proposals.** Despite the institutionalization of the Program Expenditure Classification (PREXC) and Results-Based Performance Management (RBPM) systems, many agencies struggle to link performance targets with budget proposals, particularly in Tier 2. Agencies often submit Tier 2 proposals with incomplete documentation, lacking clear cost-benefit analyses, baseline data, or logical frameworks. Reports frequently show that agencies fail to justify additional funding with measurable outcomes, particularly for new or expanded programs (ADB, 2013).²² Proposals were also poorly linked with the Philippine Development Plan (PDP), Medium-Term Fiscal Framework (MTFF), Budget Priorities Framework (BPF), and other sectoral roadmaps. As a result, proposals are often rejected given the very limited fiscal space.
- 3) 2TBA encourages reliance on historical budgeting which weakens performance and outcome evaluation.** Implementing agencies including oversight entities often rely heavily on historical budgeting practices that prioritize financial figures over actual physical performance. Instead of assessing whether a program is delivering results, funds are allocated based on what was spent during the previous year, which undermines the principles of performance-informed budgeting. Indeed, absorptive capacity serves as a useful indicator of an agency's ability to utilize funds. However, it should not be the primary measure of performance. Historical budgets tend to carry forward inefficiencies, including outdated priorities, poorly performing programs, or

²² See also *National evaluation policy framework: Guidelines on evaluation in the national government*

duplicative activities (OECD, 2019). Greater emphasis must be placed on evaluating actual physical outputs and outcomes to ensure that budget allocations translate into tangible results and meaningful public service delivery.

VII. WAYS FORWARD

The DBM has made progress in advancing PFM reforms and enhancing the budget process. However, in light of the increasing complexity of national budget preparation, there is a growing need to further strengthen the process by ensuring it is genuinely holistic, transparent, and participatory—not only in principle, but also in practice, particularly in the evaluation and decision-making stages.

On procedural matters particularly in the absence of comprehensive operating guidelines for evaluation. To achieve a more credible and transparent budget preparation process, there is a need to establish a published Budget Operations Manual for NGAs and GOCCs. This can be mandated through a provision under pending PFM reform legislation strengthening inter-agency evaluation of performance and budget proposals. The manual must include the following, among others:

On Procedural Matters

- The role of relevant oversight agencies (e.g., DBM, DoF, DEPDev) to strengthen coordination and evaluation of budget proposals, linking planning and budgeting.
- The publication of internally issued budget advisories to promote greater transparency and accountability, enabling all stakeholders—including implementing agencies, CSOs, and congressional oversight bodies—to better understand the evaluation process. Greater clarity on certain technical aspects—such as the consistent application of indexation policies (i.e., which items are adjusted for inflation and which are not)—would help ensure predictability and consistency across agencies.
- Budget Preparation Calendar that includes regular TBH with agencies for Tier 1 level which should be elevated to the Cabinet and the President consistent with the original intent of 2TBA.
- Consistent application on i) benchmarking at the NEP level or the GAA level; ii) the details on the level/amount of ICT PAPs to be included under Tier 1 or Tier 2; and iii) amount to be provided for multiyear projects supported by MYCAs, to name a few.

- Revival of the DBCC Sub-Committee on Program/Project Appraisal (SC-PPA), previously used by the DBM, with the help of the DoF, DEPDev, Governance Commission for the GOCCs, and other key stakeholders. This can also serve as an avenue for both Houses of Congress to establish formal channels in evaluating more thoroughly Tier 1 and Tier 2 proposals.
- Optimizing the role of CSO participation providing value on the inputs of CSO partners, highlighting how their recommendations were considered in the crafting of the Tier 1 and Tier 2 proposals of implementing agencies.

Establishing a more uniform set of guidelines in a single budget document, with all relevant policies included, will promote transparency and fiscal responsibility (Alesina & Perotti, 1996), help reduce ambiguity, and ensure that all stakeholders operate under a shared understanding of the budget preparation process.

On issues related to Fiscal Discipline, Allocative and Operational Efficiency. Given the widening gap between government resources and spending requirements, it is imperative to rigorously assess the potential trade-offs and unintended consequences of incremental and historical budgeting under the 2TBA. The following policy options may be considered:

- Reassess the impact of the 2TBA on fiscal sustainability and consider integrating it with a ZBB approach to enhance budgetary control. A modified zero-based approach, which requires justifying select program expenditures from scratch, could provide a more rigorous framework for managing the growing fiscal deficit.
- To effectively link the use of performance information in evaluating funding proposals, it is recommended to continue strengthening the results-based budgeting framework that ensures stronger alignment between annual budget allocations and performance outcomes. This requires embedding monitoring, evaluation, accountability, and learning (MEAL) systems across government agencies to systematically track progress, assess performance, and link funding to measurable results.
- Consider reviving the Results-Based Monitoring, Evaluation and Reporting Policy – Inter-Agency Technical Working Group and the Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Bureau, previously created under National Budget Circular No. 565²³ in-charge with oversight, steering and coordinating functions in pursuit of the intent for synchronized and more effective monitoring and evaluation system in the public sector.

²³ *Adoption of a Results-Based Monitoring, Evaluation and Reporting Policy (2016)*

- Performance and financial data from NGAs must be consistently utilized in budget formulation and oversight. Strengthening the integration of performance metrics into budget decisions will help ensure that government spending directly supports priority development outcomes, enhances public service delivery and promotes transparency and accountability.

Ultimately, Congress plays a pivotal role in turning these goals into reality. By advancing key public financial management (PFM) legislation—such as the Budget Modernization Bill—lawmakers have the opportunity to reshape the budget process into one that is truly transparent, accountable, and strategically aligned with national priorities.

Despite the positive contributions of the 2TBA, the evidence for causality remains suggestive rather than conclusive. Future research should aim to isolate the specific impacts of 2TBA from concurrent reforms, institutional adjustments, and external shocks like the pandemic. Thorough public expenditure reviews should investigate shifts in funding between priority and non-priority sectors, examine the ratio of new versus ongoing programs in budget allocations, and track whether increased appropriations translated to improved sectoral outcomes. Such reviews must be supported by comprehensive agency-level data to inform future assessments and should be tackled in subsequent policy research or discussion papers.

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ANNEX

DISTINCTIONS OF 2TBA BY EXPENSE CLASS

Particulars	Tier 1	Tier 2
Personnel Services (PS)		
CFAG*	(1) Salary and allowances of all filled and unfilled positions reported in the Government Manpower Information System (GMIS) as of end of current year, (2) pension payments for existing retirees, (3) retirement gratuities	(1) pension payments for new retirees as of cut-off date (i.e., after end of December, CY)
Other Agencies	(4) salary of all filled positions are lodged under regular agency budgets 30% of the PS cost of unfilled civilian position is placed under Miscellaneous Personnel Benefits Fund (MPBF)	
all agencies	(5) other standard allowances, benefits and incentives of filled positions, (6) other non-interface PS items of filled positions, as well as existing authorized allowances and collaterals of Military/Uniformed Personnel (MUP), (7) step increments, (8) lumpsum for DBM-approved/authorized Casuals and Contractuals, (9) Terminal Leave (TL) benefits of compulsory retirees both civilian and MUP positions	(2) adjustments in PS due to budget policy decision such as: implementation of a new program or activity, abolition or expansion of P/A/P; major change in the organizational structure of an agency; and transfer of functions between agencies, (3) additional contractual/casual positions for ongoing PAPs
Specific Agencies	(10) 100% of the PS cost of new positions based on population-based formulas (e.g., teaching and MUP positions, among others), (11) 100% of the PS cost of new troops under DND-AFP and DOTr-PCG, (12) 100% of the PS cost of unfilled positions: MUP in PNP, BJMP, BFP, PCG, NAMRIA, and BuCor, teaching positions and military personnel in the DND, (13) 75% of the PS cost of unfilled medical and medical-allied positions, (14) Retirement Gratuity of compulsory retirees of MUPs and agencies covered by special laws, (15) Pension payments for existing retirees of CHR	100% of the PS cost of new positions and staffing modifications approved by the DBM after end of calendar year, up to the prescribed cut-off date; up to 75% of the PS cost of new civilian positions proposed for creation and staffing modifications with legal basis, established standards, or with evaluation based on complete agency submission of documentary requirements, Step Increment due to Meritorious Performance per CSC-DBM JC No. 2012-1, and proposed overtime pay requirements per CSC-DBM JC No. 2015-2.
For inclusion in MPBF	(1) 30% of the PS cost of unfilled civilian positions, except those provided otherwise, (2) Medical allowance of qualified civilian personnel as subsidy for the availment of HMO-type benefits, pursuant to EO No. 64, s. 2024, subject to DBM Guidelines are included under Tier 1 of MPBF	(1) 100% of the PS cost of new positions and staffing modifications approved by the DBM after December 31, 2024 up to the prescribed cut-off date, (2) up to 75% of the PS cost of new civilian positions proposed for creation and staffing modifications with legal basis, established standards, or with evaluation based on complete agency submission of documentary requirements, (3) Step Increment due to Meritorious Performance per CSC-DBM JC No. 2012-1, and (4) Proposed overtime pay requirements per CSC-DBM JC No. 2015-2

For inclusion in the PGF	Pension payment for existing retirees as of December 31, 2024 for MUP positions and agencies covered by special laws	(1) TL for Optional retirees, (2) RG for optional retirees of agencies covered by special laws, (3) Pension payment for NEW retirees for MUPs, and agencies covered by special laws, (4) Monetization of leave credits, (5) Separation benefits and/or incentives of affected personnel pursuant to reorganization, streamlining, rightsizing, organizational optimization efforts, full implementation of devolution of functions to LGUs, merger/consolidation
MOOE	(1) Funding requirements to implement ongoing P/A/Ps, (2) Budget requirements for regular periodic activities or programs (PSA Survey, COMELEC election), (3) Resources required for the pursuit of existing or ongoing initiatives in promoting and enhancing agency performance, including improved public service delivery, (4) Regular and recurring services covered by contracts or Multi-Year Contractual Authority (MYCA), (5) approved locally funded projects covered by MYCA, (6) Maintenance cost of existing critical and strategically important non-financial assets, facilities, camps/bases, among others, to ensure their continued operation, (7) approved FAPs covered by Forward Obligational Authorities and Loan Agreement, (8) Ongoing ICT P/A/Ps, which are in accordance with the DICT-endorsed ISSP, and endorsed by the MSC, (9) Others not provided in the FY 2025 NEP covering the following: Reasonable costs needed to ensure the operation of newly-completed facilities and camps/bases, as of December 2024 -taking into account any reductions in existing costs; and Office accommodation and equipment costs for newly-approved filled positions, (10) Budget requirements for the ongoing implementation of the FHE for SUCs and the CHED	(1) Funding requirements to cover new/expanded existing P/A/Ps, as identified under the PDP and BPF, (2) MOOE costs to implement approved major changes in the organization or structure of an agency, including downsizing or mergers, (3) MOOE costs not included in the FEs due to changes in demand-driven parameters of Medium-Term Expenditure Plans (MTEP); and already approved rolling development or expansion plans, (4) Proposed resources needed for pursuing initiatives in promoting and enhancing agency performance, including improved public service delivery, (5) New/expanded ICT P/A/Ps, (6) Maintenance costs and spare parts for projects to be completed by current year,
For inclusion in the budget of ALGU	(1) Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao i.e., Annual Block Grant, Special Development Fund, Share in Taxes, Fees, and Charges; and (2) LGUs i.e.. National Tax Allotment, Special Shares of LGUs in the Proceeds of National Taxes, Barangay Officials Death Benefits, Special Shares of LGUs in the Proceeds of Fire Code Fees and Local Government Support Fund	(1) New/expansion of subsidy support to LGUs, (2) Adjustments based on submission of certifications or endorsements received beyond the deadline of the submission of Tier 1 for the funding requirements to cover the transfers from the NG to the LGUs, including BARMM
CO	(1) cost of ongoing infrastructure and non-infrastructure capital projects that have been approved in previous years, (2) approved locally funded projects covered by MYCA, (3) replacement of Motor Vehicles, (4) Capitalized maintenance cost and spare parts of existing critical assets to ensure their continued operation, (5) Basic CO requirements of newly completed facilities, camps/bases, buildings, and newly approved filled positions	(1) Proposed new infrastructure projects included in the PIP and TRIP, (2) New major capital projects (MCP) to be implemented starting FY 2026 and ongoing MCPs, (3) Proposed requirement for the purchase of electric vehicles, when available in the market and/or in the locality, for additional/newly-entitled officials and/or functions of a newly-created agency

Both MOOE and CO	(1) Approved LFPs covered by MYCA subject to revision to reflect the cash requirements that shall be paid within the year in consideration, (2) Approved FAPs covered by FOA and Loan Agreement, (3) Ongoing ICT P/A/Ps, which are in accordance with the DICT-endorsed ISSP, and endorsed by the Mithi Steering Committee	(1) New/expanded ICT P/A/Ps, New FAPs due for negotiation in FY 2025 and implementation in FY 2026 as contained in the programming documents of the lending institutions/ donor/ grantor as certified by the DOF.
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* Congress, Judiciary, COA, CHR, COMELEC, CSC and Ombudsman

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